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Deliverable D8.1

3D model of infected lung epithelial cell

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WP 8 – SARS-cov2 host cell remodelling	UHEI	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	31.12.2022

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CoCID Report, WP8 T8.1

The deadlines for the two main tasks of WP8, T8.1 and T8.2, fall respectively in December 2022 and 2024. The pandemic years were a unique time, during which world-wide intense scientific efforts were channeled on SARS-CoV2 research, accelerating tremendously the pace of discoveries in the field. In this respect we summarize the work done so far which exhausted a good part of the planned tasks for WP8, and we further outline some preliminary experiments for the investigation of Dengue viral replication via SXT which will be continued in RP2.

T8.1 To reconstruct SARS-CoV-2 induced 3D intracellular phenotypic modifications (Lead: UHEI, participants: UKHD, SiriusXT)

During the period RP1, the group of Ralf Bartenschlager (UKHD) UKHD carried out cell culture work to find the best conditions to maintain virus stocks and to find suitable cell models to enable the study SARS-CoV2 by SXM as well as other techniques. UKHD and others were able to address the major points of T8.1, i.e. the characterization of the changes to overall cell architecture of lung epithelial cells Calu3 upon SARS-CoV2 infection, using plastic room temperature EM in the form of FIB-SEM and TEM tomography. The study confirmed the dramatic remodelling of endoplasmic reticulum and Golgi, revealing changes to organelles distribution and sizes (Cortese et al., 2020) and offering a blueprint of the overall changes at a 5 nm isotropic resolution.

The complete EM datasets from this work are available for download on EMPIAR—ID 10490, and are additionally viewable in an interactive manner via MoBIE, an open access Fiji plugin for 3D data visualization and sharing.

The plastic EM investigations are affected by sample preparation limitations and are time consuming, requiring about 2-3 days to image each cell via FIB-SEM and additional lengthy preparation procedure to preserve the sample in plastic. Therefore SXT was still necessary to confirm that these changes occur on a larger number of cells and to be able to effectively compare different cell lines and the virus variants that emerged during and after the time of these experiments.

To this end, we expanded our focus to studying via SXT differences in cell cultures infected by different viral strains. UKHD prepared and distributed to the collaborators at Sirius XT samples using A549 ACE2 TMPRSS2 cell line that is permissive to both the Wuhan and Omicron variant of the SARS-CoV2 virus, as confirmed by immunofluorescence (Fig 1 panels c, d, e and f).

The rationale behind this experiment is to apply SXM to elucidate possible differences in the replication organelles (double membrane vesicles) shape, distribution and relationship to other cellular structures among the two variants, making use of the higher throughput, high resolution and whole cell field of view enabled by SXM.

As controls, UKHD provided the **partners** (SiriusXT, CSIC, UCD and UHEI) with both mock non-infected cells that were chemically fixed prior to vitrification as per biosafety level 3 experiments and samples of A549-ACE2 cells labelled with fluorescent live-cell markers, that were frozen with/without prior chemical fixation, with the aim of performing dual observation in SXM and in cryo light microscopy (**Fig 1 a and b**).

Fig 1: a – Live-cell acquisition of A549 ACE2 TMPRSS2 cells grown on gold finder grid, C2/2, 24 hours post seeding, stained with nuclear (cyan) and mitochondrial (red) cell permeant dyes prior to freezing. b- detail of image a, showing a typical random cells distribution in the central part of the grid.

c- Immunofluorescence of A549 ACE2 TMPRSS2 cells grown on coverslips for 16hours and infected with Wuhan strain SARS-CoV2 virus at MOI=5. Nucleocapsid is shown in green and double stranded RNA in red, nucleus in Cyan. d- detail of image c showing the relative distribution of dsRNA signal, corresponding to the replication organelles grouped in the perinuclear region and nucleocapsid proteins being distributed all over the cell.

e- cell treated as described above, but with Omicron SARS-CoV 2 virus variant. f - Detail of e, showing the same relative distribution of replication organelles and nucleocapsid.

Imaging with the SXT-100 microscope (Fig 2) confirmed the possibility to clearly observe some of the cellular organelles in the infected cells, such as lipid droplets and elongated structures probably part of the cytoskeleton. Despite some of the organelles being remarkably visible,

these tomograms displayed poor overall contrast when compared to samples that had not been chemically fixed prior to freezing. In particular, the nucleus appears very opaque, overshadowing the surrounding area. An example of the decreased transparency and loss of contrast of the samples upon fixation is illustrated in Fig2.

Loss of contrast upon fixation is a common problem which also affects cryo EM techniques, and is a logical consequence of the “flattening” in the chemical differences within the subcellular structures upon linking with aldehydes. On the other hand, a strict fixation procedure is necessary for the inactivation of the virus. Therefore in the next experiments we will take advantage of the experience gained by WP6 and WP9, and tune the fixation protocol for SARS-CoV2 to improve contrast, while ensuring complete inactivation.

Fig 2: Left: SXM zero tilt projection of A549 SARS-CoV2 infected cells fixed with 4%PFA and 1.25%GA. Cells, especially at central part where the nucleus is, are darker and display reduced contrast than the cells of the right. Right: SXM zero tilt projection of A549 uninfected cell, unfixed prior to plunge freezing.

Despite the lower transparency, the colleagues at Sirius XT were able to tune the imaging settings to acquire a handful of tomograms for both Wuhan and Omicron infected A549 cells (Fig.3). Some of the imaged cells display a large crowding of vesicular structures in the perinuclear region of the A549 cells, consistently with the data previously acquired in FIB-SEM for the Calu3 cells, showing as a major striking feature the formation of numerous double membrane vesicles in the cytoplasm. We are further developing image analysis strategies to quantify the changes and planning correlative SXT to EM experiments to confirm the identity of the viral organelles in a correlative fashion.

Another limitation to tomographic acquisition comes from the random positioning of the cells on the surface of the grid. Only the cells that are located central to a grid square are accessible to be imaged in tomography, as especially at high tilts the grid bar will come into the field of view for less ideal positions. The “well located” cells correspond to only a small fraction of the sample. To this end, UKHD is experimenting with micropatterning of the grids, which will help obtain a more favorable distribution of the cells, achieving both a higher number of locations to be imaged per grid, and an increased exposure to the liquid propane during plunge freezing, thus improving at the same time the ice quality and the overall throughput of the technique.

While the cell culture on micropatterned cells is already established for the BSL2 cell culture condition, additional experiments and protocols development is required for BSL3 level pathogens such as SARS-CoV2 and Dengue virus.

Micropatterning, combined with the addition of the integrated light microscope in the SXT-100, which enables screening of the grid for optimal targets prior to SXT acquisitions, will improve the efficiency of acquisition and allow for more convenient correlative workflows.

Fig 3: Tomographic slice (45nm thick) through a reconstructed tomogram of A549 cell infected with SARS-CoV2 Wuhan strain, scale bar 2 μ m. Lipid droplets are indicated with yellow arrows, the nucleus is labelled N in blue and the red arrows indicate cytoskeletal elements.

T8.2 To identify whether SARS-CoV-2 induced intracellular remodelling is independent from the infected cell type (Lead: UKHD, participants: UHEI, SiriusXT)

In T8.2 the use of SXT will be expanded to comparative analysis of SARS-CoV2 infection in cell lines. Cell culture conditions and infectivity were investigated for the following cell lines, and cellular rearrangements were observed via electron microscopy.

Cell type	infectivity	EM imaging	Morphological rearrangements
A549-ACE2	++	+	++
A549	+	+	n.d.
Calu3	++	+	++
HEK 298	++	+	++

Vero E6	++	-	++
NPG	++	-	n.d.

Table adapted from Cortese et al. 2020

Following these results, UHEI and UKHD successfully prepared HEK293T-ACE2, A549-ACE2, and Calu3 cells infected with SARS-CoV2 that were loaded in capillaries and imaged at the Berkeley synchrotron, giving high resolution rapid observation, at the whole cell level and in label-free conditions, of perturbations induced by SARS-CoV2 infection in this cell type (Loconte et al., 2021), as summarized in **Fig 4**. Data acquired for this publication are available from download at Mendeley data at the DOI: 10.17632/gkc557ssvp.2 .

This study confirmed the presence of double membrane vesicles and convoluted membranes in the perinuclear region, consistently to what observed via EM and in other cell lines. The D8.1 3D model of lung epithelial cells at different stages of infections is thus concluded.

Fig 4 The hallmarks of SARS-CoV-2 infection. Virtual slices and 3D renderings of the entry of viral particles (A), the large compartment found in three cells, showing high density and heterogeneous structure of the compartment (B), double membrane vesicles (C), convoluted membranes (D), whole multinucleated cell (E). Each organelle is color coded as follows: nucleus - blue, mitochondria - green, lipid bodies - yellow, vesicles - cyan, virions - magenta, DMVs - red, CMs - orange, and large compartment - gray. Scale bars, 2 μ m.

Two aspects for the future work on commonalities and differences of SARS-CoV2 infected cell types (D8.2) are currently in focus: 1) improvement of the automatic segmentation of cellular anatomy available to the partners for CoCID, part of WP8 and 2) integration of capillary holder for the whole cell analysis to the Lab-SXT (WP4).

To increase statistical significance of the results and speed up data analysis of the SXT images, we combine previously developed open-source tool biomedisa with machine learning based on the cascaded U-Net. At the moment we achieved 97% accuracy for automatic segmentation cell cytoplasm and nucleus, see Fig.4. The results of automatic segmentation of cell structure will be presented at SPIE Medical Imaging in 2023.

Fig 4 Automatic segmentation pipeline with 3D U-Net network added to the semiautomatic segmentation Biomedisa. The network is trained on 43 datasets. 10 datasets are automatically segmented with the dice score of 0.9760 and pixel-wise accuracy of 0.9718.

Having achieved a good part of the proposed tasks for WP8 to the study of SARS-CoV2 infection, we plan to further leverage the power of SXT in following the progression of other viruses. We chose to use dengue virus (DENV) in Huh7 cells that are highly permissive for DENV and have a cell morphology that is well accessible via both capillary based and grid-based SXT. Based on immunofluorescence data, we are preparing samples for SXT imaging at 24 and 48 hours post infection. These specimens will be analyzed by both whole cell imaging with synchrotron-based SXT and correlative with electron and fluorescence microscopy with Lab-SXT.

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